

A Critical Inference of Sri Aurobindo's *The Blue Bird*

¹C.Parkavi, II M.A English Literature, MSUC College, Nagalapuram, Tamil Nadu.

²S.Loganayagi, II M.A English Literature, MSUC College, Nagalapuram, Tamil Nadu.

Abstract

Sri Aurobindo was one of the most memorable spiritual leaders of India. He was in essence an intellectual, a poet, a philosopher, and above all a yogi. His activities as a writer can make it give the impression as though he led four or five different lives in a single lifetime. His creativity and muse came from his practice of yoga and ascension to superior states of mind and consciousness. He wrote extensively on Yoga and his poetic genius epitomized in his classic work Savitri. The poem The Blue Bird is a poem of symbolizing Aurobindo himself in deciphering the endless freedom in the sea of ordinary life. Hence, a decisive study is made in this paper to appreciate the value of the poem.

Keywords: Sri Aurobindo, Creativity, Spirituality, *The Blue Bird*.

Sri Aurobindo's *The Blue Bird* has the rather providential capability to transcend worlds. In the Indian cultural framework birds enjoy a rather splendid place. They are well thought-out as representatives and medium for the Gods. For e.g.: The Eagle or Garuda for Lord Vishnu, The Crow for Saturn, The Swan for Brahma and many more. This simple reception of the power and position, bestowed upon it by God, is perceptible in the very first stanza of the poem "I am the bird of God in His blue... For the gods and the seraph's ear. (B.B 1-4). The poem has been written in first person narrative, the internal monologue of the poem soliloquizes the poet's own meditation on the experiences of the Blue Bird.

The poet himself remains entirely indistinguishable while adopting the persona of the Blue Bird. While the poem is purely descriptive, it is richly garish with the poet's own imagination as well to tell its matchless state. The sky is "griefless", the soil is "suffering" and the Blue Bird has a "burning heart" reveals the richness in its state. The preference of words is as wide and expansive as the flight of the Blue Bird whose "My Pinions soar beyond Time and Space Into unfading Light" (5). The Blue Bird is eternal because it conveys "the bliss of the Eternal's face and the boon of the Spirit's sight." (6-7)

Sri Aurobindo adheres to a right arrangement in the assonance in order to create harmony. The pure rhyming pattern "ab, ab" is identical, with the second line in each quatrain ending on a rising note. This is extra reinforced by the meter, which is a loose iambic tetrameter. As a variation some of the lines [*Divinely high and clear or Into unfading Light*] pack four accents in a very short space as in. At this time, the line appears to give a sense of purposefulness to the bird's flight. The choice of a short meter also implies an uncomplicated yet meaningful symbol, for which the poet would like the reader to assume interpretation. *The Blue Bird* is a descriptive poem replete with images both literal and abstract. Occasionally both may appear in the same line as in this case.

Sri Aurobindo's Blue Bird is a mystical who has witnessed all. His liberty is born of true knowledge, "Nothing is hid from my burning heart" and as a result he has a mind that is "shoreless and still" that determines his life course and not personal impulse.

Hence, the symbols in poetry are the personification of the poet's own thoughts and feelings. Sri Aurobindo cannot be separated from the poet. His use of the Blue Bird as a symbol goes far beyond its literary allusion and reflects his own consciousness. *The Blue Bird* is the epitome of freedom, wisdom and happiness born out of a joining of will, with that of the Eternal's uniqueness.

References

1. **Aurobindo, Sri.** *Collected Poems*. Pondicherry: Sri Aurobindo Ashram, 2009.
2. **Satprem.** *Sri Aurobindo or the Adventure of Consciousness*. Sri Aurobindo Ashram, Pondicherry, 1970.
3. **Dalal, A.S.** *A Greater Psychology: An Introduction to Sri Aurobindo's Psychological Thought*. New York: Jeremy P. Tarcher/Putnam, 2001.

Cite this Article in English (MLA 8 Style) as:

¹Parkavi, C. & ²Loganayagi, S. "A Critical Inference of Sri Aurobindo's *The Blue Bird*." *Literary Druid*, Vol. 2, no. 1, January, pp. 9-10. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3606657.

Author (s) Contribution Statement: Nil

Author (s) Acknowledgement: We acknowledge our sincere thanks to our Professors'

Author (s) Declaration: We declare that there is no competing interest in the content and authorship of this scholarly work.

The content of the article is licensed under [Creative Commons Attribution4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) International License.